

IMPLEMENTING INTERACTIVE LESSONS**Amonova Gulnora Zarifovna**

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Teacher of School number № 44

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12635643>

Annotation: Interactive learning is replacing traditional lecture-based education. With technological advancements and real-time interactive lectures, it's increasingly essential for schools, educational institutions, and training centers to embrace this educational method. Incorporating interactive learning into online e-learning courses can revolutionize how students absorb and retain information. This approach enables live interaction between students and instructors, as well as among students themselves during sessions.

Key words: Student engagement, mobile devices, interactive strategies, creative images, interactive games.

Introduction

Interactive lessons involve learners actively collaborating with teachers and peers while engaging in the subject matter. The most effective interactive lessons provide numerous opportunities for students to discuss, collaborate, and participate in learning activities. These lessons can be designed for both synchronous and asynchronous instruction, often utilizing digital tools to enhance student engagement. In literacy instruction, interactive lessons are crucial for helping students improve their reading, writing, speaking, and thinking skills

Main part

Teachers encounter new generations of students daily who are deeply immersed in technology and social media. Hence, it is crucial for teachers to learn how to integrate classes with new interactive materials afforded by mobile devices and their numerous features. Utilizing interactive learning strategies in the classroom enhances education, making students feel more motivated and engaged. The goal is to leverage the ease with which students use tablets to incorporate them into class activities, thereby fostering participation and interaction.[1.56].

As you know, text-heavy lectures can be tedious, leading to a loss of student interest. To maintain their engagement, consider incorporating multimedia elements into your sessions such as: Creative images, Informative graphs, Pictographs, Podcast clips, Short video lessons, and News or movie clips

You don't need to tirelessly search the internet for relevant information or visuals; you can create them yourself. There are numerous free online tools available to help you generate engaging images and graphs.[2.101]

Struggling to Make Lessons Interactive?

One of the significant challenges is finding resources that facilitate interactive learning and keep all students engaged. Some students may be reluctant to share ideas or initiate conversations, making it harder to maintain their engagement. To address this, incorporate interactive lessons with specific roles and responsibilities to increase accountability and engagement, similar to the Literature Circles found on Raz-Plus. Clear expectations can encourage students to participate more actively in learning activities and discussions, allowing them to learn from one another through interaction.[1.56].

Creating Effective, Interactive Lesson Plans

To ensure your interactive lessons are effective, provide constructive and actionable feedback to students. This feedback can take various forms, but the goal is to help students improve their skills and achieve learning objectives. For more specific ideas on providing effective feedback, check out interactive lessons in programs like Foundations A-Z and Writing A-Z, which offer tips for planning and delivering immediate, corrective feedback. These lessons often incorporate a gradual release of responsibility, promoting collaboration, idea-sharing, and partner work.[4.1].

Interactive Games for Learning

Interactive games can motivate students and spark their enthusiasm for learning. These digital tools combine game elements with learning objectives, making education engaging. Interactive games can be effective across all subjects, including vocabulary instruction. Vocabulary development is essential for better comprehension, but planning engaging vocabulary instruction can be challenging. Consider integrating interactive vocabulary games and activities into daily lessons.[3.2]

Premade lessons in Vocabulary A-Z, for example, offer assignable, digital game-based activities that engage students. These activities help students practice and enhance their vocabulary, phonics, and spelling skills, and are often linked to texts within Raz-Plus, enabling students to make connections to familiar content. Regardless of your approach to vocabulary instruction, interactive games are valuable for supporting student learning.

Summary

Considering all into account, stimulating interactive environment in the classroom requires a collaboration between teachers and students. In this way, digital tools can go a long, in terms of keeping all students focused and interested on a particular topic thereby enhancing their comprehensive ability. Hence, teachers should stay informed about how to do it and what challenges or factors should be taken into consideration.

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